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TRANSREGIONAL COOPERATION IN CRISIS CONDITIONS: POSSIBILITIES OF PUBLIC MANAGEMENT ADAPTATION

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Abstract

Transregional cooperation under the challenges of instability is considered, which forms a number of options for overcoming crisis phenomena.

The role of public governance in promoting and supporting local initiatives, as well as regulatory control and prevention of violations of legislation, is studied.

Features of increasing the ability to identify the unfolding of the crisis and predict its impact are established. The processes of concentrating efforts on the implementation of anti-crisis regimes of transregional cooperation and cross-border cooperation are analyzed. The purpose of the article is to establish the features of modern transregional cooperation in crisis conditions. The article uses well-known methodological tools of public administration sciences (comparative and institutional analysis) and well-known general scientific methods (prognostic, inductive). The development of European aid aimed at supporting cooperation in innovative sectors is studied. The circumstances under which the regions are planning new achievements and developments in the presence of a common level of development are being clarified. Clearly, cohesion benefits Europe as a whole and each individual territory.

The important anti-crisis measures are the fight against unemployment and ensuring the employment of the population. The factors in the crisis conditions are being clarified, a number of territories are losing stability and growth prospects. It has been proven that the anti-crisis experience of the EU is useful for many neighboring territories. It was concluded that the wartime experience demonstrated the ability of Ukrainian society to act unitedly and quickly under extraordinary circumstances.

Keywords: transregional cooperation, public governance, modernization, crisis, forecasting, adaptation.

Formulation of the problem

In the conditions of ongoing military operations in Ukraine, the relevance of international cooperation and the search for ways to optimize and modernize the management of socio-economic development of the regions is increasing. Effectiveness of sustainability strategies and approaches to transition to a new level of functioning of the state and society depends on the effectiveness of adaptive mechanisms for coordinating international interactions and contacts between levels of public governance. Transregional cooperation forms a number of options for overcoming crises phenomenon

They are: decentralization of the supply of goods and services, flexibility of planning, the possibility of correcting the trajectory of directions and terms of interregional communication. In the conditions of modern information and digital technologies, the network of transregional contacts ensures the disclosure of the economic, sociocultural and demographic potential of regions based on self-organization and self-reproduction of innovative activity. Public administration still has the role of promoting and supporting local initiatives, as well as regulatory control and prevention of violations of legislation.

The imperatives of European integration require stimulation of the initiative to scale up positive experience, engagement of citizens of institutes and organizations with the needs of increasing the number of contacts and increasing their effectiveness. Concentration of efforts on the implementation of anti-crisis regimes

of transregional cooperation and cross-border cooperation requires considerable attention.

Analysis of publications. Anti-crisis measures of public governance attract the attention of many Ukrainian scientists. In particular, Yu. Barabanova demonstrates the interregional asymmetries of the modern state of logistics management in Ukraine [1], V. Prykhodko analyzes interregional economic cooperation in the environment of cross-border asymmetries in the context of sustainable spatial development [3], L. Firsova demonstrates the role of the project "Development of the Interregional Technology Transfer Network" in the innovative development of regions [5].

At the same time, there is a need to outline the prospects of transregional cooperation in the conditions of the crisis economic and political environment.

The purpose of the article is to establish the features of modern transregional cooperation during the war period, crisis conditions.

The task of the article is to identify optimal approaches to adapting the public governance system to crisis challenges and maintaining the level of interaction between regions.

Basic content:

Transregional cooperation acts as a factor in the optimization of activities aimed at improving the interaction of regions and cities within the EU. The tools of this cooperation are a number of programs that ensure the stability of relations and the level of mutual exchanges.

European aid is aimed at supporting cooperation in innovative sectors. According to the analytical material "Cooperation creates sustainability", regions and cities can use four interregional Interreg programs (ESPON, Interact, Interreg Europe and URBACT). From green transition to employment, from migration to public health.

Our joint session at the European Week of Regions and Cities will offer concrete examples of cooperation within four programs that can help local and regional authorities build resilience and support their economies and citizens [8].

Stimulation of transregional cooperation is carried out on the basis of optimization of territorial development. Awareness of the problems and prospects of the development of administrative and territorial units directs the EU funds to equalize indicators of economic growth and social well-being. In the presence of a common level of development, the regions are planning new achievements and developments. The document on the cooperation program within the framework of transregional cooperation shows that the implementation of all EU strategies should fully take into account the territorial dimension and limit their potentially negative differential impact.

The goal of the Territorial Agenda for 2030 is to strengthen territorial unity in Europe. This means securing a future for all places, creating equal opportunities for citizens and businesses wherever they are located. Territorial cohesion strengthens cooperation and solidarity and reduces inequality between more prosperous and less prosperous places [9].

The goals and tasks of sustainable development in the territorial agenda ensure the application of anti-crisis measures and programs. A common understanding of the future forms the synchronicity of investments and development directions for many regions. Accordingly, public administration adapts territories to crisis conditions. Cohesion benefits Europe as a whole and each individual territory. To strengthen cohesion, the Territorial Agenda provides strategic guidelines for spatial planning and strengthening the territorial dimension of relevant policies at all levels of governance.

The Territorial Agenda 2030 outlines two main goals: a fair Europe that offers future prospects for all places and people; A Green Europe that protects our shared livelihoods and shapes processes of social transformation. These goals are divided into six priorities for the development of the European territory [9].

Anti-crisis strategies of transregional cooperation are related to activities related to approximation of the basic orientations of the general welfare society. The "Interreg Europe 2021-2027" program document presents the characteristics, situations and perspectives of European regions with regard to the challenges and strategic orientations described above, which are very diverse. The uniqueness of each region also has enormous added value for other regions of Europe through various forms of mutual learning. It lays the foundation for the programme's role in Europe's quest for a smarter Europe, a greener, climate-neutral and sustainable Europe, a more connected Europe, a more social Europe and a Europe closer to its citizens [9].

The socio-economic development of the regions of the modern EU is determined by unevenness. Socio-cultural and infrastructural problems cause different approaches to the implementation of joint projects and programs. An important anti-crisis measure is the fight against unemployment and ensuring the employment of the population. According to European reports, there are large and persistent gaps between regions in terms of employment and unemployment, with unemployment rates significantly higher in Southern Europe and the outermost regions. The employment situation of workers over 50 years old also remains a problem for most countries. The data also indicate a worsening of the employment level of 35–49-year-olds [9].

A significant anti-crisis tool is investing in joint initiatives that are related to the economic and social needs of the regions. The purpose of financing is the development of the institutional capacity and self-sufficiency of the regions of the importance of such measures. The first direction focuses on investments in interregional projects, and the second supports the development of value chains in less developed regions. It allocates a small budget for capacity development, not for public administration [9].

The innovative nature of pan-European tools for strengthening transregional cooperation makes it possible to reveal the potential of regions and identify the directions of pan-European development. The anti-crisis experience of the EU is useful for many neighboring territories. The experience of stimulating anti-crisis transregional cooperation is comprehensively evaluated and analyzed by the expert community. Accordingly, Interreg Europe projects aimed at innovation can become the basis for future interregional innovation investments depending on the lessons learned from the cooperation and the possible identification of areas for joint investments [9].

An important direction for the modernization of transregional cooperation in the EU is the introduction of modern information technologies. It is about the recording of extraordinary events and the dissemination of information about anti-crisis measures and practices. [7].

Horizontal transregional cooperation is an important factor in the implementation of reforms and crisis management practices. On the example of specific institutions and institutions, optimal approaches for increasing contacts and solving common problems and realization of common interests can be seen.

We also want to develop international cooperation between hospitals, improve interaction between emergency services. [11].

Health care cases show that specific regions can implement effective crisis adaptation practices. Subsequently, these practices spread to the rest of the European regions. The role of public governance is to facilitate the fastest possible implementation of innovations and ensure the removal of artificial formal barriers. This is extremely important because health care is something very personal, very close to people's cultural background, and it takes years to build strong agreements with people from different cultural backgrounds [11].

The example of cooperation in the field of health care shows the possibility of unifying the practices of anti-crisis activities at the interregional level. These practices are recorded in management activities at the EU level. "30 years ago, we saw that cross-border workers could benefit from health care on both sides of the border. [11].

Areas of anti-crisis cooperation between regions within the EU are of a broad strategic nature. Setting up transregional cooperation programs is aimed at large-scale joint actions to build infrastructure and improve interactions in various fields. EU programs usually define specific goals for interregional cooperation. According to the "Interreg NEXT" programme, EU cooperation programs with neighboring regions cover 184 regions with 260 million people in 33 countries and are located along the EU's external borders. [10].

The reaction of the European community to crises caused by Russia's military aggression is an important element in building a unified approach of the European community in terms of reactions to unprovoked large-scale actions. The neighborhood program is adjusted accordingly. This means the exclusion of Russia and its satellites from the perspective innovation space of the EU. According to the European program "Interreg NEXT", after the Russian military aggression against Ukraine and in accordance with the restrictive measures of the EU. [10].

The strategic goals of the European instruments of anti-crisis transitional cooperation have not only an applied but also a valuable nature. Program strategies are defined around the EU's goals for a smarter, greener, more connected, more social Europe and the neighbourhood, as well as meeting regional needs for effective governance cooperation and safer borders.

Ideas and plans for transregional cooperation at the EU level go far beyond the tasks and priorities of individual regions. In the "Interreg NEXT" program, special attention is paid to green and digital transitions in the dimension of cooperation, which is a mandatory requirement aimed at protecting the globally important natural heritage in the region of the Barents Sea, the Baltic Sea, the Danube and the Carpathians, the Black Sea and the Mediterranean basins. Digitalization is gaining importance as an end-to-end factor that transforms society and the economy. Involvement of civil society and youth in the process of implementation and decision-making [11].

The presented material shows that the European community's multidimensional response to crisis challenges includes activities and the development of conceptual bases for the management of transregional cooperation. The anti-crisis potential of tools and programs of European integration makes it possible to attract broad sectors and significant resources. For modern Ukraine, improving transregional cooperation within the EU and with neighboring countries is an opportunity for deeper assimilation of integration practices and gradual alignment of Ukraine's development with other European countries.

Therefore, transregional cooperation in the conditions of martial law in Ukraine changes parameters and implements adaptive mechanisms. The cases of the countries of the modern EU prove that under modern conditions it is possible to redistribute resources, manage migration flows, monitor the intensity of contacts

and exchange processes. Interregional cooperation and solidarity of the EU countries have proven their ability by creating mechanisms for humanitarian crisis prevention, coherence and efficiency of management. Large volumes of cargo flows and population became possible thanks to prognostic capabilities and operational monitoring of the situation.

In the context of the European integration of Ukraine, institutions of public power need to learn the practices and approaches of anti-crisis support for transregional cooperation, as well as a proactive and proactive position regarding the post-crisis recovery of the identification of the state of crisis. Accordingly, there is a need to form flexible regimes of extraordinary cooperation. In particular, it is about the exchange of known information, the coordination of plans, the development of interactive results-oriented activity indicators.

The system of public governance should encourage the growth of direct transregional contacts, as well as carry out transformations aimed at restructuring interactions. It is a matter of transregional cooperation in attracting investments in technologies of new management and production practices. An important task in changing the vector of transregional cooperation is revealing the potential of Ukraine's regions, presenting their institutional capacity and openness to new initiatives.

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